

A Study on the Problem Faced by the E-Consumers of Online Shopping in Chennai

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Kalpana, R., and

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“A Study on the Problem Faced by the E-Consumers of Online Shopping in Chennai.” *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 150–55.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3412548>

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Abstract

Nowadays most of the people use technology in their daily life due to busy work schedule. Saving time is one of the benefits of consumer to purchase the product or service through online in their hectic schedule. Ecommerce (electronic commerce) denotes the buying and selling of goods or services offered by the e retailers using the internet, and the handover of money and data to perform these transactions. Electronic Commerce has emphasised impact on the lives of modern people here in the Chennai city. Though E-Commerce helps the consumer to make an easy and convenient shopping to save the cost of transportation and time, but there are some problems faced by them regarding their own privacy and personal information, difficulty in contacting seller etc. So, the researcher intended to study the problems faced by the consumers of e commerce. This study is descriptive in nature, both primary and secondary data were used. The researcher has collected data from 150 online consumer in Chennai by convenience sampling method. The information was gathered with help of structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The statistical tools like simple percentage and garret ranking test were used to analyse the collected data. Even though, E-Commerce is popular and used immensely the study revealed that consumer has met some difficulties such as Difficult to contact Seller, Difficult to change defective product, Delivery conditions changed after transaction, Visual differences between picture and received goods and difficulty in getting answers for our queries. From the results it was evident that the main problem faced by the consumer is unable to contact seller after getting product. So the researcher suggest that e-retailer must pay attention to consumer expectation to contact seller. More over product it was suggested to sell a good quality product in order to avoid delivering the defective products. Moreover the online shoppers must have awareness to take care of their security/privacy and personal information. They should avoid buying products from unknown sites to avoid defective product as well as wrong goods, to prevent theft of credit and debit card information. Effective steps should be taken to enforce laws to ensure consumers security and satisfaction towards ecommerce. Care must be taken by the Ecommerce retailers to develop and promote trust and relationship among consumers.

Key words: e-commerce, online shopping, damaged products

Introduction

In the last decade e-commerce runs all around over the globe and it has used for business in form of electronic with help of computer and Internet. Internet network works as a bridge to connect the business people, it is known as business to consumer, Business-to-business and consumer-to-consumer. Due to the unavailability of time, busy work schedule and convenience in shopping it has attracted the consumers for Banking, shopping, payments and Services. Shopping is one of the habits. Consumer does not like to heat, humidity, noise and air pollution associated with road-side and way side shopping and also for the consumers lacking confidence on bargaining and preferring to avoid crowded places. So, that they move on online shopping. Although consumers like to shop from a bricks and motor, they feel very convenient to purchase online since it frees and save their valuable time from personally visiting the store. The benefits of online shopping to reduce the effort of travelling time to store. The convenient of online shopping is consumer can searching products from their home or office and wherever they wish to compare and select the product. Ecommerce provide the great opportunity for 24/7 means we can purchase no time limitation. And also it offers the consumer a huge range of products coupons, gifts etc. Demand for products that international product which not available elsewhere. So consumer searcher their availability of product through online. It is one of reason for ecommerce to grow faster.

Review of Literature

Vanitha & Prakash (2016) studied that the common problems faced by customer in online shopping Coimbatore and the study has suggested that fake products should be verified before delivery and the problems in case of online shopping should be avoided and better service should be provided.

Kumar & Kasthurimeena (2017) have studied that customer problems towards online shopping in Coimbatore. The study has concluded that online shopping the customers should have knowledge about usage of internet and computer. Internet has become the centre of not only our personal and social lives, but also our business and professional lives

Ramesh & Kumar (2019) have studied that Problems faced by online customers – A Garret Ranking Approach. The study has revealed that the respondents' ranking for the seven factors which are mostly confronted by the online buyers at present. It has observed from result that majority of the respondents have chosen to give rank 1 to the factor 'Product Variation', followed by 'Faulty products' (rank-2) and Delay in Delivery (rank 3). The respondents have assigned the least rank to the factor 'Payment problems'. The factors delay in delivery and return back the items are ranked third and fourth, respectively.

Sivanesan (2017) has studied that Problems Faced by Customers in Online Shopping in Kanyakumari. The studies has revealed that the majority of the customers are faced the problems line can't touch and feel and delivery point is not available to interior. It has also found that the customers feel that delivery of the product is one week and more than one week.

Objective of the Study

To ascertain the problem faced by the consumers of online shopping in Chennai.

Research Methodology

This study is descriptive in nature, both primary and secondary data were used. The researcher has collected data from 150 online consumer in Chennai by convenience sampling method. The information was gathered with help of structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The statistical tools like Simple Percentage and Garret ranking test were used to analyse the collected data. The Garret ranking was used to find out the ranking distribution pattern of customers in online shopping.

Significance of the Study

Electronic Commerce has emphasised impact on the lives of modern people here in the Chennai city. Though E-Commerce helps the consumer to make an easy and convenient shopping to save the cost of transportation and time, but there are some problems faced by them regarding their own privacy and personal information, difficulty in contacting seller etc. This study has enabled us to gather the views of online consumer in Chennai with respect to what are the problems faced by consumer in online shopping.

Table 1 Demographic Variable of the Respondents

Demographic factors	Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	62	41%
	Female	88	59%
	Total	150	100%
Age	Below 20	41	27%
	21-30 Years	58	39%
	31-40 Years	32	21%
	41-50 Years	14	9%
	Above 50 Years	5	3%
	Total	150	100%
Educational	Professional Degree	34	23%
	Post Graduation	18	12%
	Under Graduation	83	55%
	Diploma	11	7%
	Schooling	4	3%
	Total	150	100%
Marital Status	Married	59	39%
	Unmarried	91	61%
	Total	150	100%
Occupation	Govt employee	26	17%
	Private employee	44	29%
	Self employee	3	2%
	Home Maker	14	9%
	Students	63	42%
	Total	150	100%
Annual Income	Less than 2 lakh	101	67%
	above 2 to 4 lakhs	31	21%
	above 4 to 6 lakhs	8	5%
	above 6 to 8 lakhs	7	5%
	More than 8 lakhs	3	2%
	Total	150	100%

Source: Primary Data

Inference

From the above table 1, it can be inferred that 59% of the respondents were female and 41% of them male were who gave their experience on online shopping. Majority of the respondents 39% of the respondents belong to the age group 21-30 years, 27% of the respondents belongs to the age group of below 20, 21% of the respondents belong to the age group 31-40, 9% of the respondents belongs to the age group 41-50 and 3% of the respondents belong to the age group of above 50. 55% were educated in UG level, 23% were educated Professional and 12% were educated PG level and followed by 7% and 3% were educated Diploma and Schooling. 61% were unmarried and 39% were married. 42% were student, 29% were private company, 17% were Government, 9% were home maker and 2% were self-employee. 67% less than 2 lakh, 21% were earning above 2 lakh – 4 lakh, 5% earns above 4 lakh to 6 lakh and above 6 to 8 lakh and 2% more than 8 lakh.

Garrett's Rank: Garrett's ranking technique was adopted to analyze the problems faced by the consumers who shop through online. The respondents were asked to rank the various constraints faced during the purchase. The ranks assigned to the above responses by the consumers were converted to scores using the formula :

Percent position = $100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_{ij}$ R_{ij} = Rank given for the i th factor by j th individual.

N_j = Number of factors ranked by j th individual

The rank have been given by the respondents for each factors (problems)

Factors	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th	9th	10th	11th	12th	13th	14th	15th	Total	Garret's Score	Rank
F1 Difficult to contact Seller	69	9	5	6	13	6	10	16	1	5	2	1	3	1	3	150		
	5865	675	345	384	780	342	530	800	47	215	80	35	93	24	45	10260	68.4	I
F2 Delivery conditions changed after transaction	7	36	4	16	2	18	6	7	5	2	7	35	2	2	1	150		
	595	2700	276	1024	120	1026	318	350	235	86	280	1225	62	48	15	8360	55.73	III
F3 Received wrong goods	3	17	37	6	21	3	1	6	5	1	3	9	29	5	4	150		
	255	1275	2553	384	1260	171	53	300	235	43	120	315	899	120	60	8043	53.62	VI
F4 Received damaged goods	9	8	13	49	1	1	11	12	4	0	1	2	12	6	21	150		
	765	600	897	3136	60	57	583	600	188	0	40	70	372	144	315	7827	52.18	VII
F5 Poor customer service	3	10	19	6	32	13	10	3	9	11	2	1	2	29	0	150		
	255	750	1311	384	1920	741	530	150	423	473	80	35	62	696	0	7810	52.06	VIII
F6 Difficult to change defective product	1	25	20	6	13	42	11	3	7	6	1	4	2	0	9	150		
	85	1875	1380	384	780	2394	583	150	329	258	40	140	62	0	135	8595	57.3	II
F7 Difficult to get answers for our queries	5	11	0	13	4	13	37	42	4	1	12	1	6	1	0	150		
	425	825	0	832	240	741	1961	2100	188	43	480	35	186	24	0	8080	53.86	V
F8 Products guarantee is not assured	3	23	1	6	14	3	12	24	29	14	0	1	0	3	17	150		
	255	1725	69	384	840	171	636	1200	1363	602	0	35	0	72	255	7607	50.71	IX
F9 Delivery time too long for purchased product	2	2	1	5	4	10	11	7	55	39	6	0	5	2	1	150		
	170	150	69	320	240	570	583	350	2585	1677	240	0	155	48	15	7172	47.81	X

F10 Visual differences between picture and received goods	9	6	35	3	13	8	3	0	7	39	6	13	3	2	3	150		
	765	450	2415	192	780	456	159	0	329	1677	240	455	93	48	45	8104	54.02	IV
F11 Complex process of order/ payment	0	4	1	10	2	2	20	8	0	13	61	10	10	3	6	150		
	0	300	69	640	120	114	1060	400	0	559	2440	350	310	72	90	6524	43.49	XI
F12 Theft of credit card information / Privacy Information.	0	0	6	2	5	25	11	4	11	5	8	42	7	4	20	150		
	0	0	414	128	300	1425	583	200	517	215	320	1470	217	96	300	6185	41.23	XIII
F13 No after sales service or inefficient after sales service	0	10	2	2	0	2	6	2	0	6	23	20	52	22	3	150		
	0	750	138	128	0	114	318	100	0	258	920	700	1612	528	45	5611	37.40	XV
F14 Confused by over choices	18	3	3	20	5	1	1	1	11	3	8	2	14	42	18	150		
	1530	225	207	1280	300	57	53	50	517	129	320	70	434	1008	270	6450	43	XII
F15 Tangibility of products	10	0	2	5	21	2	1	14	2	6	10	7	3	27	40	150		
	850	0	138	320	1260	114	53	700	94	258	400	245	93	648	600	5773	38.48	XIV

Table 2 Problems faced by e-Consumer of Online shopping in Chennai

Factors	Total	Mean Garret's Score	Rank
F1 Difficult to contact Seller	10260	68.4	I
F6 Difficult to change defective product	8595	57.3	II
F2 Delivery conditions changed after transaction	8360	55.73	III
F10 Visual differences between picture and received goods	8104	54.02	IV
F7 Difficult to get answers for our queries	8080	53.86	V
F3 Received wrong goods	8043	53.62	VI
F4 Received damaged goods	7827	52.18	VII
F5 Poor customer service	7810	52.06	VIII
F8 Products guarantee is not assured	7607	50.71	IX
F9 Delivery time too long for purchased product	7172	47.81	X
F11 Complex process of order/payment	6524	43.49	XI
F14 Confused by over choices	6450	43	XII
F12 Theft of credit card information / Privacy Information.	6185	41.23	XIII
F15 Tangibility of products	5773	38.48	XIV
F13 No after sales service or inefficient after sales service	5611	37.40	XV

Interpretation

There are many factors which affect the consumer behaviour in online purchase. From the table.2 shows analyses the problems faced by the e-consumer in online shopping. The Table reveals the respondents' ranking for the fifteen factors which are mostly confronted by the online buyers at resent. It has observed from result that majority of the respondents have chosen to give rank I to the factor 'Difficult to contact Seller', followed by 'Difficult to change defective product' (rank-II), Delivery conditions changed after transaction,(rank-III), Visual differences between picture and received goods (rank IV) and Difficult to get answers for our queries (rank V). The factor No after

sales service or inefficient after sales service and Tangibility of products are least rank XIV and XV respectively

Suggestions

The majority of the customers have faced the problems while transacting through Online. From the study it was evident that the main problem faced by the consumer is unable to contact seller after getting product. So the researcher suggest that e-retailer must pay attention to consumer expectation to contact seller. More over it was suggested to sell a good quality product in order to avoid delivering the defective products. Moreover the online shoppers must have awareness to take care of their security/privacy and personal information. They should avoid buying products from unknown sites to avoid defective product as well as wrong goods, to prevent theft of credit and debit card information. Effective steps should be taken to enforce laws to ensure consumers security and satisfaction towards ecommerce. Care must be taken by the Ecommerce retailers to develop and promote trust and relationship among consumers.

Conclusion

The main objective of the study is to ascertain that what are problem faced by the consumers of online shopping in Chennai. This study has concluded that there are many problems faced by e-consumer online shopping. The benefits of online shopping is gaining popularity among people specially the teenage groups but nowadays to become equally popular among all age groups online shopping will have to cover a longer distance. The study has revealed that even though online shopping has more advantages of most of the customers have favourable attitude towards online shopping but it also majority of the consumer suffer due to unnecessary defective product to receive. So they should take care to improve their environment to avoid damaged goods before delivery to the consumer.

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